

Advancing Sustainability in Textiles: Integrating EMS, Circular Innovation, and Cleaner Production.

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ABSTRACT:

In the rapidly evolving textile, apparel, and fashion (TAF) industry, there is an urgent need to integrate sustainability principles into design and development processes, while moving away from synthetic textiles in commercial apparel manufacturing. The multifaceted impact of textile waste, particularly from fossil fuel-based fabrics, has emerged as a global crisis, significantly harming ecosystems and contributing to what can be termed the "textile anthropocene." This literature review focuses on supply chain management as a critical area for intervention.

Key industry publications, including the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) report on "Sustainability and Circularity in the Textile Value Chain: A Global Roadmap" (2023) and the Textile Exchange's "The Future of Synthetics" (April 2024), serve as foundational references for this review. This literature review critically examines the claim from the Textile Exchange publication that suggests eliminating synthetic materials from the industry is not necessarily the solution.

To ensure a comprehensive analysis, the review references literature on Environmental Management Systems (EMS), Cleaner Production Practices (CPP), Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM), and Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM) from the past four years, highlighting the rapid advancements and ongoing challenges in the textile sector. One alarming finding is that the carbon footprint of waste polyester recycling is approximately ten times greater than that of virgin polyester production, underscoring the urgent need for transformative change.

By collaborating with textile supply chains to adopt innovative technologies and sustainable materials, the industry can foster the critical changes necessary for a more sustainable future. This review ultimately advocates for a balanced approach that recognizes the complexities of material usage while pushing for significant sustainability advancements within the TAF value chain.

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1. **Introduction:**

The textile industry significantly contributes to the ongoing triple planetary crisis (UNEP, 2022; 2023), exacerbating climate change and highlighting the urgent need to mitigate carbon emissions from its value chains (Leal Filho et al., 2024). Fast fashion, characterized by cheap synthetic fabrics and poorly made mass-produced apparel, consistently raises sustainability concerns about excess production, consumption and associated environmental impact of textile waste (Centobelli et al., 2022). The reliance on petroleum-based resources for manufacturing synthetic polymers further complicates the issue, indicating a critical reliance on unsustainable and non-renewable resources (Wren, 2022).

Throughout the lifecycle of synthetic textiles, substantial waste generation poses significant anthropogenic challenges (Malizia & Monmany-Garzia, 2019; McCay & Mehta, 2024), contributing to microfiber fragmentation and environmental pollution (Li et al., 2023; Lim et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2021; Napper et al., 2023; Priya et al., 2023; Surana et al., 2024). Organizations such as The Microfibre Consortium (TMC) and UNEP acknowledge the detrimental effects of fiber fragmentation. Notably, fiber shedding is not exclusive to polymer-based materials; it can occur from all types of fabrications (Allen et al., 2024; Palacios-Marín et al., 2022).

Transitioning from synthetic fabrics to sustainable alternatives presents significant challenges, including economic constraints, technological limitations, and consumer behavior, underscoring the complexity of addressing these environmental issues within the textile industry (Abbate et al., 2023; Bhandari et al., 2022; Hossain et al., 2024). The environmental and health challenges associated with synthetic textiles transcends production processes, posing substantial risks to ecological systems and human health (Chen et al., 2022; Singh & Bhalla, 2017; Wani & Kumari, 2020).

The prevalent use of synthetic polymers, in the creation of poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) and polypropylene-based textiles, provides mechanical strength beneficial for swim and activewear garments. However, these same attributes contribute to various ecological hazards, including the release of hazardous chemicals (Amarakoon et al., 2022; McCay & Mehta, 2024). Phthalate esters (PAEs) commonly found in synthetic textiles are associated with endocrine disruption, reproductive toxicity, and potential carcinogenic effects (Aldegunde-Louzao et al.,

2024). Furthermore, per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), which are utilised for their water-repellent and antibacterial properties, exacerbate environmental degradation (Chen et al., 2022). Contaminants of concern (CECs) leaching from apparel-related plastics lead to persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in textile wastewater, posing a significant environmental threat (Kounina et al., 2024; Lellis et al., 2019; Singh & Kumar, 2024).

Addressing the use of hazardous synthetic materials is urgent to mitigate their environmental impact throughout their lifecycle. Ensuring sustainability within the textile industry and preventing ecotoxicological risks, including the bioaccessibility, biomagnification, and bioaccumulation of harmful substances in the environment, is critical.

Aims/Objectives: This literature review explores essential strategies for systemic transformation within the textile sector. It compares and assesses optimization strategies within supply chains, frameworks for change, and the feasibility for implementing advanced sustainability and circularity practices. An examination of the required investments to support or bolster Environmental Management Systems (EMS), Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM), Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM), and Cleaner Production Practices (CPP) is also included. Strategies aimed at reducing the industry's dependence on virgin resources in synthetic textile production, while minimizing associated emissions, are crucial for driving innovation and mitigating the environmental impacts of the textile sector. Special emphasis will be placed on advancements in textile-to-textile recycling and biosynthetic innovations.

Roadmap: To address these challenges, the paper proceeds in three parts: first, analysing the role of EMS in regulating environmental accountability; second, evaluating the adoption of cleaner production practices and their systemic limitations; and third, assessing circular innovations, including textile-to-textile recycling and biosynthetic alternatives, as pathways to long-term sustainability.

2. **Methodology:**

This literature review was conducted through a systematic and comprehensive examination of both industry publications and academic journals, using resources from Griffith University's online library database and Scopus. The review employed a structured search strategy, incorporating specific keywords and Boolean operators to identify relevant qualitative literature on the environmental impacts of synthetic textiles, as well as sustainable practices within the textile industry.

The search terms included combinations such as “synthetic fabric*” OR “synthetic textile*” AND “microfibre pollution” OR “microplastic pollution” OR “textile pollution” OR “fabric pollution” to address the environmental impacts associated with synthetic textiles. To investigate sustainable production practices and frameworks, additional search terms like “environmental management system* in fashion” OR “EMS in fashion,” “cleaner production” OR “cleaner production practices” AND “fashion industry” OR “textile industry” were used.

Further searches were conducted using terms such as “sustainable supply chain management” OR “SSCM” AND “fashion industry” OR “textile industry,” as well as “sustainable supply chain management” OR “SSCM” AND “ISO14001” to examine the integration of sustainability standards within the sector. Policy measures and assessment techniques relevant to sustainability were explored through searches for “extended producer responsibility” OR “EPR” AND “fashion industry” OR “textile industry” and “life-cycle assessment” OR “LCA” AND “fashion industry” OR “textile industry.”

Finally, to investigate innovative advancements in the textile sector, searches were performed using terms such as “textile recycling” OR “textile-to-textile” AND “fashion industry” OR “textile industry,” and “biobased polyester” OR “biosynthetics” AND “fashion industry” OR “textile industry.” All selected articles were screened for relevance and inclusion based on their alignment with the review's focus on the environmental impacts and sustainability strategies within the synthetic textile industry.

3. Improving production practices within supply chains:

Systemic transformation of the textile sector is crucial for reducing reliance on synthetic textiles, synthetic-blends, and dyes (Sahimaa et al., 2023). A comprehensive approach which encompasses product design and production processes is essential to shift consumption patterns and transition the industry towards closed-loop manufacturing and a circular economy (Centobelli et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2021). Current practices in textile manufacturing and waste management must incorporate policy changes and key interventions aimed at enhancing sustainability and prioritizing ethical production (Palacios-Mateo et al., 2021). The irresponsible disposal of textile waste has significant negative environmental impacts (Khairul Akter et al., 2022; Kumar et al., 2021), highlighting the need for urgent action.

Promoting organizational values aligned with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) across the entire value chain is essential for advancing corporate social responsibility (CSR) and adherence to environmental, social, and governance (ESG) principles (Pedersen et al., 2016). The implementation of sustainable business models, including cleaner production (CP), cradle-to-cradle practices, life cycle analysis (LCA), and collaborative consumption, positions organizations more favourably in a competitive market (Pedersen et al., 2016; Rhodes, 2019). Organizational and change management interventions (CMIs) are vital in supporting, involving and reinforcing efforts to reduce emissions and achieve long-term sustainability (Hagl et al., 2024), ultimately providing a competitive advantage to those who prioritize these initiatives (Ly, 2021).

The ongoing dependence on virgin fossil-fuel-derived feedstocks perpetuates unsustainable practices in the textile industry (Textile Exchange, 2024). To address these issues, it is essential to integrate improved practices through innovation and technology, requiring collaboration among various stakeholders, including supply chains, technical organizations, and policymakers (UNEP, 2023). In developing and emerging economies, the adoption of advanced technologies may encounter significant economic barriers to change, stemming from inadequate infrastructure, the hierarchical structure of tiered suppliers, and limited availability of sustainable materials (Alam et al., 2023; Alayón et al., 2022; Bhandari et al., 2022).

In an industry where competitive advantage often relies on trade secrets and proprietary business models, a lack of transparency can hinder progress toward systemic change (Gardner et al., 2019). Ensuring transparency and traceability within supply chain operations is critical for the sustainable transformation of the apparel sector (Aakanksha & Aravendan, 2023; Madumali et al., 2023; Ospital et al., 2023). Engagement and education of stakeholders who are otherwise reluctant to embrace sustainable and circular transitions are essential for advancing the industry toward net-zero goals. Facilitating transformation requires radical innovations in material science and circular energy practices to redesign fashion and textile supply chains, thereby establishing reliable and sustainable operations (Stahel, 2021; Patnaik & Tshifularo, 2021).

While apparel brands can influence style and production volume, the responsibility for enhancing textile options and manufacturing practices primarily lies with sustainable supply chain innovation (SSCI) (Aladaileh et al., 2024). Optimization strategies within the textile value chain are vital for enhancing sustainability and operational efficiency, particularly through the roles of Tier 1 to Tier 4 suppliers (UNEP, 2023; Villena & Gioia, 2018). Although policy frameworks play a significant role in guiding these strategies, focusing on technological advancements across supplier tiers enables a deeper understanding of production schedules (Lorente-Leyva et al., 2024).

Computer-based Discrete Event Simulation (DES) models facilitate multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) to manage risks within production planning (Ferro et al., 2021), which is vital for reducing production waste and enhancing Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM) practices (Nazir et al., 2024). Further analysis of sustainable strategies through Quality Function Deployment (QFD) could benefit supply chains in the assessment of environmental vulnerabilities, particularly within emerging economies (Chowdhury & Quaddus, 2015; Erdil, 2019; Roy et al., 2020). These methodologies support risk reduction and enhance supply chain performance across four key dimensions: economic, environmental, operational, and social (Geng et al., 2017).

Sustainable manufacturing processes within the textile sector rely on integrating the Internet of Things (IoT) to foster future-oriented decision-making and tech-driven environmental-strategies, enhancing production through high-quality data and analytics (Orisadare et al., 2024; Petrillo et al., 2024). Digitalisation platforms

such as the newly released Lectra ai software Valia Fashion will aid in the collaboration between brands and manufacturers to streamline production (Lectra, 2024). Transitioning long-held business models to a smart, lean, and green paradigm has the potential to significantly augment performance (Fiorello et al., 2023). However, the success of these frameworks largely hinges on stakeholder engagement within the supply chain (Iyere & Misopoulos, 2022) and the enhanced development of sustainable replacements for synthetic textiles (Egan & Salmon, 2021).

Ultimately, to ensure textile supply chain resiliency (SCR), it is crucial to adopt collaborative (SCC) and integrative (SCI) approaches that effectively manage production-related challenges, including energy consumption and environmental risks (Ahmed et al., 2020; Dissanayake & Weerasinghe, 2021; Sharma et al., 2023). Evaluating the trade-off between economic productivity and environmental impact is vital; therefore, sustainable evaluation methods must guide raw material producers and manufacturers to implement practices that optimize eco-efficiency and diminish emissions (Jiang et al., 2016; Luo et al., 2021).

The traditional approach to minimizing pre-consumer textile waste (Azad et al., 2024) has proven inefficient, underscoring the need to enforce frameworks that transition current practices from linear to circular production models. Despite ongoing efforts, existing methods have been inadequate to address the environmental impact of textile waste and its associated issues (Tang, 2023). This situation necessitates urgent action to embrace sustainable production technologies and innovative frameworks to repair the ecological and financial damages caused by the sector (Salmi & Kaipia, 2022; Rahaman et al., 2024).

It is vital for raw material suppliers within tiers 4 and 3 to leverage the symbiotic opportunities provided by national and international regulatory bodies to facilitate essential industry-wide changes and promote best production practices. Regulatory instruments, such as command-and-control systems, can be effective at this stage of the industry's sustainability journey; however, the reliability of these regulations to control the output of virgin synthetics and ensure compliance with carbon footprint (CFP) and LCA standards remains a concern (Abagnato et al., 2024; Resta et al., 2016; Wiedemann et al., 2023; Xu et al., 2018). Ultimately, the adoption of innovative technical practices allows suppliers to improve operations while prioritizing environmental impact reduction. Collaborative efforts among lower-tier

suppliers are essential for driving meaningful advancements in sustainability within the textile sector, thereby contributing to a more sustainable textile value chain.

3.1 Pathways for Effective Environmental Governance:

The implementation of Environmental Management Systems (EMSs), as refined by the International Standard ISO 14001:2015, is crucial for mitigating the environmental impacts of synthetic textiles within the industry and the broader environment. Effective EMS adoption requires organizations to prioritize environmental stewardship and develop internal policies that guide and motivate structural changes (Wang et al., 2022). This involves recognizing and assessing the negative consequences of synthetic textile production, calculating their excessive use of natural resources, and measuring the emissions generated throughout all stages of manufacturing (Muthu, 2020; Shamsuzzaman et al., 2023).

Through the process of LCA (ISO 14040:2006) and Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), organizations can adopt an Organisational-Life Cycle Assessment approach to evaluate their environmental impact (Resta et al., 2016). Prioritising Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) reveals that economic productivity of synthetic textile production is significantly outweighed by the environmental costs associated with large-scale textile waste (Luo et al., 2021).

A strong EMS framework enables organizations to address critical challenges, including greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, biodiversity loss, and water resource depletion (Li & Wu, 2017; UNEP, 2023). Such frameworks require organisational leaders to definitively commit to environmental responsibility, acknowledging the pollutive aspects of synthetic textile production, the widespread impact of textile waste, and the associated risks of fibre fragmentation (McCay & Mehta, 2024). Long-range planning and the development of internal policies and procedures will facilitate the prevention and remediation of environmental impacts related to synthetic manufacturing (Iqbal et al., 2022). By clearly defining roles and responsibilities within organizations and aligning operations with global climate goals, the textile industry can significantly reduce its environmental footprint, contributing to a more sustainable future.

3.2 *Designing Systems for Improved Practices:*

The transition of the textile sector to improved environmental practices necessitates regulatory drivers for the effective implementation of EMS. Self-regulation within this industry is complex, making collaboration among stakeholders crucial for the successful adoption of EMS (Demirel et al., 2018). Initiatives such as the Fashion Industry Charter for Climate Action (UNFCCC, 2018) have set ambitious environmental objectives, including the goal for 100% of priority materials to have a low climate impact by 2030 and for 45% of polyester to be recycled by 2025. However, current trends indicate that the continued use of virgin polyester continues to outpace that of recycled polyester (Textile Exchange, 2024). This disparity highlights the need for regulatory oversight and pressure from industry lobby groups to encourage textile supply chains to vigorously adopt EMS practices (Li & Wu, 2017).

To fulfill the global responsibility of environmental protection, a proactive approach within the industry is essential (Zhou & Jin, 2023). This approach should include planning actions aimed at continually improving best practices in textile production and adopting sustainable processes (De-La-Flor et al., 2024; Hossain et al., 2024; Lorente-Leyva et al., 2024). While implementing environmental policies can be challenging due to significant financial and time sacrifices (Iqbal et al., 2022), these initiatives can be positively correlated with organizational performance. However, the introduction of forced regulations within the textile sector could lead to negative consequences. The vast scale required for implementing EMS may be hindered by individualised production process and the roles of stakeholders (Latip et al., 2022).

Therefore, increasing transparency across all textile value chains is critical, as is the internal documentation of systems that address environmental issues arising during manufacturing (Kumari et al., 2024; Luoma et al., 2022). Future-proof strategies that foster collaboration and integration across all supply chains within the textile sector will be pivotal in driving meaningful change through innovative planning and impactful improvements (Chourasiya et al., 2024; Islam et al., 2020). The following tables will illustrate the integration EMS frameworks and the negative associations with return on investment and product outcomes.

Table 1. Qualitative comparison of various EMS methods in the textile supply chain:

Study	Country/Sector	Subject	Method	Major Findings
Iqbal et al., (2022)	Pakistan	Importance of environmental policy on firm performance for the textile industry: A contextual study of Pakistan.	Cross-sectional method (causal melding approach and descriptive analysis by Smart PLS (Partial Least Squares)).	Researchers determined substantial investments made in EMS will result in increased costs and diminished benefits.
Li and Wu (2017)	China	EMS adoption and operational performance – China textile and apparel firms.	Quantitative statistical data to obtain financial ratios (ROA, ROS, and SOA), and operational performance.	Decrease in profitability, sales, and inventory productivity.
Lo et al., (2011)		The impact of environmental management systems on financial performance in fashion and textiles industries	Empirical evidence on performance impact EMS in fashion and textiles industries (FTIs). EMSs a passport to FTIs business.	Objective data to verify EMS benefits not confirmed. Research gap regarding the impact of EMS on firms' performance.

3.3 *Evaluating Supply Chain Sustainability Initiatives:*

Sector-wide sustainable manufacturing adopts a comprehensive and systemic approach to production (Leahu-Aluas & Burstein, 2010), emphasizing the transition from an end-of-life focus to a proactive opportunity framework (Chan et al., 2024; Chourasiya et al., 2024). Shifting from reliance on virgin raw materials to utilizing sustainable or recycled sources, particularly in synthetic textile manufacturing, requires a systematic and well-supported phase-out of conventional materials (Textile Exchange, 2024; UNEP, 2023). Such changes are projected to significantly reduce the environmental impact associated with synthetic textiles, addressing pollution and natural resource depletion (Gonzalez et al., 2023).

Sustainable manufacturing practices not only enhance environmental performance but may yield economic benefits, offering a competitive advantage within the supply chain (Prasad et al., 2020). Collaboration among stakeholders—

including producers, innovators, and recyclers—is essential for improving operational efficiencies in the textile sector and driving positive change (Abdelmeguid et al., 2024). To successfully implement Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM) initiatives, particularly in the production of synthetic apparel and fast fashion, companies must embrace circular business models while enhancing operational performance (Roy et al., 2020; Wren, 2020). However, without a clear understanding of the urgent need to reassess their product offerings, the fast fashion sector risks exacerbating the ongoing triple planetary crisis (Roberts et al., 2023).

In the context of organizational environmental objectives, allocating necessary resources and conducting audits by external consultants are essential components to influence CSR within the textile sector (Thorisdottir & Johannsdottir, 2020). Critical in the steps to ensure the success of sustainability initiatives aimed at greening supply chains, validating sustainability claims and combatting industry-wide greenwashing (Kumar et al., 2017).

Quality Management Systems (QMS), specifically ISO 9001:2015, are essential for the textile sector to enhance compliance with environmental standards and regulatory directives. Integrating ISO 9001:2015 with ISO 14001 not only solidifies the supply chain's commitment to environmental sustainability but also signals the organisation's dedication to sustainable operations through robust management frameworks (Zimon et al., 2022; Zimon et al., 2020). Implementing QMS allows organizations to verify their environmental operations and achieve SSCM (Kafetzopoulos et al., 2015; Kumar et al., 2023). Controlling eco-friendly manufacturing protocols among tiered suppliers—from raw materials to finished products—and assessing product performance throughout the lifecycle (Fritz, 2022; Shekarian et al., 2022), will enable the industry to refine textile supply chain production processes (Javaid et al., 2022).

This approach facilitates continuous improvement within the sector, driving suppliers toward more efficient, environmentally responsible, and ethical practices, exceeding sustainability and circular quality standards (Zimon, 2020). Additionally, goals such as green procurement and sustainable sourcing can significantly enhance industry objectives and provide valuable insights into the sustainability efforts of others (Govindan et al., 2021; Resta & Dotti, 2015; Srisawat & Srisawat, 2020).

At this stage of developing sustainability considerations within the textile industry, overcoming economic and financial barriers remains a significant challenge (Abbate et al., 2023; Bhandari et al., 2022; Rahaman et al., 2024). Hence, a multi-criteria decision-making approach is necessary to successfully implement eco-initiatives (Gonçalves et al., 2024). Ultimately, effective management and proactive decision-making will provide an IoT-driven production planning framework for the textile sector (Stulga et al., 2022). Identifying risks across all manufacturing processes and throughout all tiers of the textile supply chain, while addressing current and future challenges (Kähkönen et al., 2023; Warasthe et al., 2022) is complex. However, Product Lifecycle Management (PLM) software (Conlon, 2020) can enhance supply chain transparency, aligning processes with waste reduction and the principles of the triple bottom line (TBL), ensuring that sustainable practices are not only adopted but scaled effectively (Hiller Connell & Kozar, 2017).

3.4 Advancing Cleaner Production Techniques in Textiles:

The concept of cleaner production in fashion industry necessitates an urgent paradigm shift in design thinking, not only among fast fashion brands but across the entire sector. This shift is critical due to the industry's reliance on fossil fuels for the production of synthetic textiles, which contributes to unsustainable practices (Changing Markets Foundation, 2021). Current trends indicate an unsustainable trajectory for the fashion industry (Dzhengiz et al., 2023; Textile Exchange, 2024), underscoring the pressing need for industry-wide changes, particularly through discussions surrounding Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) (Centobelli et al., 2022; Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2024). Tangible change must originate from the design offices of fashion brands, focusing on the re-education of designers in eco-design principles, also known as Design for the Environment (DfE) (DCCEEW, 2022; Lifset et al., 2023).

The implementation of science-based targets initiatives (SBTi) across the value chain highlights the carbon-intensive nature of synthetic textile production, generating significant scope 3 emissions (SBTi, 2017). Addressing this issue requires an intensive decarbonization program for the textile production sector to transition toward cleaner fabric manufacturing (Leal Filho et al., 2024; Peng et al., 2022). Alarming, the carbon footprint of waste polyester recycling is approximately

ten times greater than that of virgin polyester production, emphasizing the urgent need to phase out synthetic textile production (Qian et al., 2021). Although progress is being made with carbon capture technologies to replace fossil-based polyester feedstocks (Textile Exchange, 2024), questions remain about the scalability of these technologies to facilitate the necessary changes before the 2030 SDG deadline. The UNFCCC's goal for the textile industry to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050 appears increasingly distant when immediate action is critical (IPCC, 2022).

The most significant advancements toward cleaner production will likely come from textile supply chains that prioritize problem-solving environmental interventions and technological advancements over initial economic performance (Cesar da Silva et al., 2021; de Oliveira Neto et al., 2022; Lindahl, 2024). The integration of environmentally sound technology (EST) (UNEP, 2024) and digitalization (Mondejar et al., 2021) may provide a responsive framework for advancing cleaner production practices, thereby decoupling environmental impacts from industrial operations (Li et al., 2017; Li & Wang, 2019; Stål & Corvellec, 2018).

To further enhance sustainability, the elimination of toxic and non-renewable raw materials through cleaner production methods is crucial for conserving water and energy while reducing environmental manufacturing risks. This approach employs an "up-the-pipe" strategy (Tremblay et al., 2023) to address textile pollutants across atmospheric, aquatic, and terrestrial environments (Liu et al., 2021; McCay & Mehta, 2024; Napper et al., 2023; Priya et al., 2023; Stanton et al., 2023; Surana et al., 2024). A forward-looking and problem-solving approach must prioritize pollution prevention and waste elimination at every stage of fabric and apparel production (Patel et al., 2021). However, the success of this environmentally focused approach depends on supply chains adopting a positive attitude toward cleaner production and establishing a balanced, multi-level strategy for sustainable growth, which would reduce long-term liabilities and enhance competitive advantage (Issa et al., 2024; Sun et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2023).

Collaboration to integrate advancements within the textile sector is essential for improving efficiency, adopting best management practices, and revising in-house environmental policies, practices, and procedures (Abreu et al., 2021; Alam et al., 2023). Redesigning systems (Patnaik & Tshifularo, 2021) for process improvements is a highly effective strategy for conserving materials and resources along the value chain (König et al., 2024). While progress is being made in substituting fossil-fuel-

based polymers with less toxic alternatives that maintain similar fabric performance characteristics, the critical question remains: can a successful LCA be achieved? (Ferreira-Filipe et al., 2021; Rosenboom et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2022).

Ultimately, incremental changes toward cleaner and circular production practices will not only benefit the environment but also enhance the long-term viability of the fashion industry.

4. Investment in supply chain infrastructure:

Significant investment in shared infrastructure across the textile recycling value chain is crucial for the industry's sustainable future (UNEP, 2023). However, recent developments indicate a troubling trend of setbacks. Robust infrastructure is essential, yet prominent textile recycling companies have faced financial difficulties. The German-based Soex Group is currently undergoing insolvency proceedings (Davis, 2024), while Swedish textile recycler Renewcell filed for bankruptcy earlier this year (Kent, 2024). These events highlight the challenges faced by key players in the industry.

Despite these setbacks, recent acquisitions and collaborations indicate a continued emphasis on textile-to-textile recycling, essential for a circular economy. Renewcell's joint operation with CIRCULOSE® (Taylor, 2024), exemplifies the importance of innovative recycling methods. Additionally, the Australian textile recycler BlockTexx® is making significant advancements in textile waste recycling, offering solutions for both fibre-to-fibre and fibre-to-product recycling (PolyTexx®), and fibre-to-agriculture (CellTexx®) (BlockTexx®, 2024). Their Chemical Separation of Fibre Technology (S.O.F.T.™) effectively processes various fabric blends, such as polyester/cotton blends, 100% polyester, and all cellulosic/man-made cellulosic fibres, enhancing the potential for resource recovery in the industry.

While challenges persist in the early integration of these recycling processes (Abrishami et al., 2024; Loo et al., 2023; Sandberg & Pal, 2024), the continued development of innovative recycling technologies and collaborative efforts highlight the critical need for sustained investment and effective management in the textile recycling sector to prevent further downturns.

Significant investment in technology and infrastructure is vital for enhancing sustainability within tiered supply chains and scaling circular business models.

Facilitating advancements in sustainability practices and providing tools and frameworks to achieve effective implementation (Matarneh et al., 2024; Sánchez-García et al., 2024). Requiring commitment from management to improve employee knowledge and experience is essential for enhancing intellectual capital, leading to improved data generation that is fundamental for successfully implementing EMS and CPP practices (Del Giudice et al., 2021; Huseyin Keles et al., 2023). Empowering employees fosters a commitment to sustainable change and enables the establishment of plant-wide goals for environmental solutions within the textile supply chain (Ali et al., 2024; Osei et al., 2023).

UNEP (2023) emphasizes the necessity of investing in infrastructure and collaboration within the raw material supply chain, aiming to improve eco-efficiency, and reduce the volume of new materials and products produced. Enhancing operations within the cut, make, trim (CMT) and garment manufacturing sectors will require substantial investment to prepare, implement, monitor and sustain CP measures (Maia et al., 2019). The global textile sector presents significant opportunities for sustainable and green investment (Kumar et al., 2022; Zhang & Berhe, 2022), necessitating the strategic unlocking of corporate funds to facilitate transformative changes. While initial implementations of GSCM efforts may encounter challenges—especially regarding the adoption of commercially available solutions—the need for action is urgent (Bar Am et al., 2020; BCG, 2020; Fashion for Good, 2020; Pinkse et al., 2024).

Barriers to infrastructure investments in the textile sector (BCG, 2020) include several key challenges:

(1) *Misaligned incentives*: The industry's focus on high profit margins, often leads to overlooked trusted relationships. Fragmented supply chains hinder cohesion and limit environmental impact opportunities, compounded by a lack of transparency across the value chain (Abbate et al., 2024; Bhandari et al., 2022; Brun et al., 2020).

(2) *Limited awareness of the opportunity*: Equity investors tend to overlook the textile sector in favour of the more glamorous fashion industry, directing their investment towards brands. However, a brand's reputation can be easily tarnished by unethical or unsustainable practices (Fashion United, 2024; Yu et al., 2023).

(3) *Absence of structured innovation process*: The lack of standardized processes across the entire textile value chain, combined with trend-driven and seasonal industry practices, introduces risk and uncertainty regarding investment success in supply chain operations (Wong & Ngai, 2022).

(4) *Lack of experience and technical expertise*: While external investors may be adept at capital raising activities and optimizing business models, their unfamiliarity with the textile industry can pose risks, acting as a significant deterrent (Pazilov et al., 2020; Ullah et al., 2020).

(5) *Incorrect perception of externalities*: Although high-risk investors may be attracted to innovative industries with potential for rapid growth, the uncertainty in the development of new materials can find them priced out of the market. This creates barriers to entry and presents challenges in competing with commoditized products (Alam et al., 2023; Nemlioglu & Mallick, 2020).

(6) *Inadequately structured exclusivity*: Stakeholders holding emerging technologies may inhibit the rapid commercialization of preventative maintenance systems, which are crucial for addressing the environmental release of synthetic fibers throughout the supply chain or the advancement of materials. This barrier is particularly concerning, as advancements may be retained by patent holders for financial gain, limiting their benefit to the broader sector (Thorisdottir & Johannsdottir, 2020).

5. Innovation in fabrication:

The textile sector is positioning itself for systemic transformation, where innovation will drive the anticipated reduction of unsustainable practices and reduce the industry's reliance on virgin natural resources for the production of synthetic products (Sahimaa et al., 2024). Propelled by initiatives that promote sustainable production and consumption, supported by the implementation of voluntary technical manufacturing guidelines and standards designed to regulate textile production (Leventon et al., 2023).

Enzymatic textile technology is noteworthy due to its reduced energy consumption, resulting in a diminished environmental impact and a lower carbon footprint. This technology offers enhanced production cost efficiency and employs more organic processes in textile manufacturing (Harsanto et al., 2023). This bio-based finishing application can be integrated throughout the textile value chain, from tier 4 raw materials to tier 1, and is applicable to synthetic textiles as well as the modification of synthetic fibers (Egan et al., 2023; Madhu & Chakraborty, 2017; Rahman et al., 2020; Silva et al., 2015; Tochetto et al., 2022).

Innovation in biodegradable synthetic textile polymers, such as thermoplastic polyester, exemplifies the potential of biodegradable materials (Egan & Salmon,

2021). These polymers are produced at scale through the fermentation of sugars to yield lactic acid monomers, presenting advantages over traditional PET textiles. However, the environmental benefits of this process hinge on the sustainable cultivation of sugarcane, as unsustainable practices may result in environmental impacts comparable to those associated with oil extraction (Palacios-Mateo et al., 2021). Bio-polyesters such as CELYS™ (2024) degrade via hydrolysis, however, questions remain regarding the biodegradability of bio-based plastics and plastic-blend textiles in marine environments (Phys.org, 2023). The source point for wastewater treatment disposal, this plays a critical role in this context (Dey et al., 2021; Napper & Thompson, 2020; Siegfried et al., 2017). LCA for green bio-based polyester fiber substitutes studies are still emerging (Ivanović et al., 2021; Shen et al., 2012). The adoption of green raw materials, low-carbon processes, green energy sources, and efficient plastic recycling methods is expected to enhance eco-efficiency in the textile industry through the replacement of synthetic textiles with these sustainable alternatives (Yang et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2020).

Advancements in textile-to-textile recycling is being driven by legislative initiatives such as California's groundbreaking Textile Recovery Act (2024), integrating LCA, EPR and principles of the circular economy into the state's recycling strategies (Chensvold, 2024). By applying a green chemistry approach to fiber separation, exemplified by the BlockTexx® method, the recycling of fibers and polymers can significantly reduce reliance on incineration or landfill disposal at the end of a product's life cycle (Sun et al., 2021). Movement toward closed-loop bio-based recycling represents a promising future direction (Ribul et al., 2021). However, until these technological advancements are scaled for global application, there remains a pressing need to limit or phase out the widespread use of synthetic textiles.

6. Conclusion:

In an industry that demands swift yet sustainable advancements, addressing the environmental impacts of synthetic textile manufacturing is essential. The reliance on fossil fuel-derived sources contributes to global warming, while the proliferation of microplastic waste adversely affects atmospheric, terrestrial, and

aquatic ecosystems. To break this cycle of “take, make, waste,” a technological and systemic transformation in textile production practices is required.

Collaboration across supply chains and among diverse cultural and geographic contexts will be vital for integrating robust environmental policies and technological innovations into production processes. Achieving genuine sustainability and cleaner production will require substantial investment from both governmental bodies and private capital, with socio-ethical investment models playing a pivotal role in empowering stakeholders to prioritise ecological responsibility.

The persistence of fast fashion’s unethical business models, combined with its dependence on synthetic textiles, underscores the urgent need for collective re-evaluation of consumption behaviours. Without such change, the industry’s detrimental cycle will continue unabated.

One possible thought experiment is whether only radical interventions — akin to a temporary industry shutdown or a collective “working bee” spanning stakeholders from raw material suppliers to governments and innovators — could reset unsustainable trajectories in textiles. While largely hypothetical, such scenarios illuminate the magnitude of transformation required if incremental cleaner production practices and voluntary corporate commitments continue to fall short.

Ultimately, empowering textile supply chains to lead this transition is imperative. By harnessing collective efforts, enforceable governance frameworks, and innovation in fabrication, the industry can begin to reconcile its environmental impacts with a more sustainable and socially responsible future.

7. **Bibliography:**

- Aakanksha, L., & Aravendan, M. (2023) Impacts of Transparency and Traceability on Fashion Supply Chain System. *Intelligent Information Management*, 15, 100-119. <https://doi.org/10.4236/iim.2023.153006>.
- Abagnato, S., Rigamonti, L., & Grosso, M. (2024). Life cycle assessment applications to reuse, recycling and circular practices for textiles: A review. *Waste Management*, 182, 74–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2024.04.016>.
- Abbate, S., Centobelli, P., Cerchione, R., Nadeem, S. P., & Riccio, E. (2023). Sustainability trends and gaps in the textile, apparel and fashion industries. *Environment, Development and Sustainability : A Multidisciplinary Approach to the Theory and Practice of Sustainable Development*, 26(2), 2837–2864. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-022-02887-2>.
- Abdelmeguid, A., Afy-Shararah, M., & Salonitis, K. (2024). Towards circular fashion: Management strategies promoting circular behaviour along the value chain, *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 48, 143-156, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2024.05.010>.
- Abreu, M. C. S. d., Ferreira, F. N. H., Proença, J. F., & Ceglia, D. (2021). Collaboration in achieving sustainable solutions in the textile industry. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 36(9), 1614–1626. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JBIM-01-2020-0041>.
- Abrishami, S., Shirali, A., Sharples, N., Kartal, G. E., Macintyre, L., & Doustdar, O. (2024). Textile Recycling and Recovery: An Eco-friendly Perspective on Textile and Garment Industries Challenges. *Textile Research Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00405175241247806>.
- Ahmed, W., Najmi, A., & Khan, A. (2020). Analysing supply chain risk management capabilities through collaborative and integrative approach. *International Journal of Business Process Integration and Management*, 10(1), 29. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJBPIIM.2020.113111>.
- Aladaileh, M. J., Lahuerta-Otero, E., & Aladayleh, K. J. (2024). Mapping sustainable supply chain innovation: A comprehensive bibliometric analysis. *Heliyon*, 10(7), e29157–. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e29157>.
- Alam, M. F. B., Hosen, M. I., Mridha, J. H., Chowdhury, S. E., & Rahman, M. A. (2023). Assessing the barriers of integrating technological innovations in textiles sector: Implications towards sustainable production. *Green Technologies and Sustainability*, 1(3). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.grets.2023.100039>.
- Alayón, C. L., Säfsten, K., & Johansson, G. (2022). Barriers and Enablers for the Adoption of Sustainable Manufacturing by Manufacturing SMEs. *Sustainability*, 14(4), 2364. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14042364>.
- Aldegunde-Louzao, N., Lolo-Aira, M., & Herrero-Latorre, C. (2024). Phthalate esters in clothing: A review. *Environmental Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 108, 104457. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etap.2024.104457>.
- Ali, S. R., Al masud, A., Hossain, M. A., Islam, K. M. Z., & Shafiul Alam, S. M. (2024). Weaving a greener future: The impact of green human resources management and green supply chain management on sustainable performance in Bangladesh's textile industry. *Cleaner Logistics and Supply Chain*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clscn.2024.100143>
- Allen, E., Henninger, C. E., Jones, C., Wood, J., & Garforth, A. (2024). Fibre fragment pollution: source directed intervention through design. *The Journal of the Textile Institute*, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405000.2024.2379307>.

- Amarakoon, M., Alenezi, H., Homer-Vanniasinkam, S., & Edirisinghe, M. (2022). Environmental Impact of Polymer Fiber Manufacture. *Macromolecular Materials and Engineering*, 307(11). <https://doi.org/10.1002/mame.202200356>.
- Azad, A.K., Haq, U.N., Khairul Akter, M.M., Uddin, M.A. (2024). *Recycling Practices of Pre-Consumer Waste Generated from Textile Industry*. In: Muthu, S.S. (eds) Sustainable Manufacturing Practices in the Textiles and Fashion Sector. Sustainable Textiles: Production, Processing, Manufacturing & Chemistry. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-51362-6_12.
- Bar Am, J., Furstenthal, L., Jorge, F., & Roth, E. (2020, June 17). *Innovation in a crisis: Why it is more critical than ever*. McKinsey & Company. <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/strategy-and-corporate-finance/our-insights/innovation-in-a-crisis-why-it-is-more-critical-than-ever>.
- Bhandari, N., Garza-Reyes, J. A., Rocha-Lona, L., Kumar, A., Naz, F., & Joshi, R. (2022). Barriers to sustainable sourcing in the apparel and fashion luxury industry. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 31, 220–235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.02.007>.
- BlockTexx®. (2024) BlockTexx®. <https://www.blocktexx.com/mission>.
- BlockTexx®. (2024). Technology. <https://www.blocktexx.com/technology>.
- Boston Consulting Group (BCG). (2020, January 22). *Financing the Transformation in Fashion*. Boston Consulting Group. <https://www.bcg.com/publications/2020/financing-transformation-fashion-investment-scale-innovation>.
- Brun, A., Karaosman, H., & Barresi, T. (2020). Supply Chain Collaboration for Transparency. *Sustainability*, 12(4429), 4429. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12114429>.
- Centobelli, P., Abbate, S., Nadeem, S. P., & Garza-Reyes, J. A. (2022). Slowing the fast fashion industry: An all-round perspective. *Current Opinion in Green and Sustainable Chemistry*, 38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cogsc.2022.100684>.
- CELYS™. (2024, January 4). *How Are Biodegradable Fibres Revolutionising Our Wardrobes and the Planet?*. CELYS™. <https://www.celys.com.au/blog/how-are-biodegradable-fibres-revolutionising-our-wardrobes-and-the-planet>.
- Cesar da Silva, P., Cardoso de Oliveira Neto, G., Ferreira Correia, J. M., & Pujol Tucci, H. N. (2021). Evaluation of economic, environmental and operational performance of the adoption of cleaner production: Survey in large textile industries. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123855>.
- Chan, E. M.-H., Cheung, J., Leslie, C. A., Lau, Y.-Y., Suen, D. W.-S., & Tsang, C.-W. (2024). Revolutionizing the Textile and Clothing Industry: Pioneering Sustainability and Resilience in a Post-COVID Era. *Sustainability*, 16(6), 2474. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16062474>.
- Changing Markets Foundation. (2021, February). Fossil fashion: the hidden reliance of fast fashion on fossil fuels. Changing Markets Foundation. <https://changingmarkets.org/report/fossil-fashion-the-hidden-reliance-of-fast-fashion-on-fossil-fuels/>.
- Chensvold, C. (2024, October 3). *Responsible Textile Recovery Act of 2024 Signed Into Law*. California Apparel News. <https://www.apparelnews.net/news/2024/oct/03/responsible-textile-recovery-act-of-2024-signed-into-law/>.
- Chen, X., Memon, H. A., Wang, Y., Marriam, I., & Tebyetekerwa, M. (2021). Circular Economy and Sustainability of the Clothing and Textile Industry. *Materials Circular Economy : Science, Engineering, and Sustainability*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42824-021-00026-2>.

- Chen, Y., Chen, Q., Zhang, Q., Zuo, C., & Shi, H. (2022). An Overview of Chemical Additives on (Micro)Plastic Fibers: Occurrence, Release, and Health Risks. *Reviews Environmental Contamination*, 260(22), . <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44169-022-00023-9>.
- Chourasiya, R., Pandey, S., Malviya, R. K., & Pujara, A. A. (2024). Towards sustainable success: A framework for assessing performance of sustainable manufacturing adoption in Indian textile industry. *Sustainable Futures*, 7, 100216–. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sfr.2024.100216>.
- Chowdhury, M. M. H., & Quaddus, M. A. (2015). A multiple objective optimization based QFD approach for efficient resilient strategies to mitigate supply chain vulnerabilities: The case of garment industry of Bangladesh. *Omega: Part A*, 57, 5–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.omega.2015.05.016>.
- Conlon, J. (2020). From PLM 1.0 to PLM 2.0: the evolving role of product lifecycle management (PLM) in the textile and apparel industries. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal*, 24(4), 533–553. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFMM-12-2017-0143>.
- Davis, H. (2024, October 8). Soex Group begins insolvency proceedings. EcoTextile News. <https://www.ecotextile.com/2024100832561/materials-production-news/soex-group-begins-insolvency-proceedings.html>.
- De-La-Flor, A., Vigil, M., & Ruiz-Ruiz, M. F. (2024). Improvement of the sustainable performance in a textile company using the lean-green methodology. *International Journal of Production Management and Engineering*, 12(1), 105–116. <https://doi.org/10.4995/ijpme.2024.20260>.
- Demirel, P., Iatridis, K., & Kesidou, E. (2018). The impact of regulatory complexity upon self-regulation: Evidence from the adoption and certification of environmental management systems. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 207, 80–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.11.019>.
- de Oliveira Neto, G. C., Correia, J. M. F., Tucci, H. N. P., Librantz, A. F. H., Giannetti, B. F., & de Almeida, C. M. V. B. (2022). Sustainable Resilience Degree assessment of the textile industrial by size: Incremental change in cleaner production practices considering circular economy. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134633>.
- Del Giudice, M., Chierici, R., Mazzucchelli, A., & Fiano, F. (2021). Supply chain management in the era of circular economy: the moderating effect of big data. *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, 32(2), 337–356. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLM-03-2020-0119>.
- Department of Climate Change, Energy, the Environment and Water (DCCEEW). (2022) Enabling Design for Environmental Good: Eco-Design Principles. https://www.dcceew.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/enabling-design-environmental-good-sub-report-eco-design_0.pdf.
- Dey, T. K., Uddin, M. E., & Jamal, M. (2021). Detection and removal of microplastics in wastewater: evolution and impact. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(14), 16925–16947. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-12943-5>.
- Dissanayake, D. G. K., & Weerasinghe, D. (2021). Towards Circular Economy in Fashion: Review of Strategies, Barriers and Enablers. *Circular Economy and Sustainability*, 2(1), 25–45. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43615-021-00090-5>.
- Dzhengiz, T., Haukkala, T., & Sahimaa, O. (2023). (Un)Sustainable transitions towards fast and ultra-fast fashion. *Fashion and Textiles*, 10(1), 1–33. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40691-023-00337-9>.
- Egan, J., & Salmon, S. (2021). Strategies and progress in synthetic textile fiber biodegradability. *SN Applied Sciences*, 4(1), 1–36. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-021-04851-7>.

- Egan, J., Wang, S., Shen, J., Baars, O., Moxley, G., & Salmon, S. (2023). Enzymatic textile fiber separation for sustainable waste processing. *Resources, Environment and Sustainability*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resenv.2023.100118>.
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation. (2024). *Pushing the boundaries of EPR policy for textiles*. Ellen MacArthur Foundation. <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/epr-policy-for-textiles>.
- Erdil, A. (2019). An Evaluation on Lifecycle of Products in Textile Industry of Turkey through Quality Function Deployment and Pareto Analysis. *Procedia Computer Science*, 158, 735–744. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2019.09.109>.
- Fashion for Good. (2020). *Financing the Transformation in the Fashion Industry*. BCG and Fashion for Good. https://fashionforgood.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/FinancingTheTransformation_Report_FINAL_Digital-1.pdf.
- Fashion United. (2024, August 27). *Exiting the clothing industry as an investor: Is this the right path to sustainability?* Fashion United. <https://fashionunited.uk/news/business/exiting-the-clothing-industry-as-an-investor-is-this-the-right-path-to-sustainability/2024082777271>.
- Ferreira-Filipe, D. A., Paço, A., Duarte, A. C., Rocha-Santos, T., Patrício Silva, A. L. (2021) Are Biobased Plastics Green Alternatives?—A Critical Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(15), 7729. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18157729>.
- Ferro, R., Cordeiro, G. A., Ordóñez, R. E C., Beydoun, G., & Shukla, N. (2021). An Optimization Tool for Production Planning: A Case Study in a Textile Industry. *Applied Sciences*, 11(18), 8312. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11188312>.
- Fiorello, M., Gladysz, B., Corti, D., Wybraniak-Kujawa, M., Ejsmont, K., & Sorlini, M. (2023). Towards a smart lean green production paradigm to improve operational performance. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 413. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.137418>.
- Fritz, M. M. C. (2022). A supply chain view of sustainability management. *Cleaner Production Letters*, 3. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpl.2022.100023>.
- Gardner, T. A., Benzie, M., Börner, J., Dawkins, E., Fick, S., Garrett, R., Godar, J., Grimard, A., Lake, S., Larsen, R. K., Mardas, N., McDermott, C. L., Meyfroidt, P., Osbeck, M., Persson, M., Sembres, T., Suavet, C., Strassburg, B., Trevisan, A., et al. (2019). Transparency and sustainability in global commodity supply chains. *World Development*, 121, 163–177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2018.05.025>.
- Geng, R., Mansouri, S. A., & Aktas, E. (2017). The relationship between green supply chain management and performance: A meta-analysis of empirical evidences in Asian emerging economies. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 183, 245–258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2016.10.008>.
- Gonçalves, H., Magalhães, V. S. M., Ferreira, L. M. D. F., & Arantes, A. (2024). Overcoming Barriers to Sustainable Supply Chain Management in Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises: A Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Approach. *Sustainability*, 16(2), 506. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16020506>.
- Gonzalez, V., Lou, X., & Chi, T. (2023). Evaluating Environmental Impact of Natural and Synthetic Fibers: A Life Cycle Assessment Approach. *Sustainability*, 15(7670), 7670. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097670>.
- Govindan, K., Shaw, M., & Majumdar, A. (2021). Social sustainability tensions in multi-tier supply chain: A systematic literature review towards conceptual framework development. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 279. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123075>.

- Hagl, C., Kanitz, R., Gonzalez, K., & Hoegl, M. (2024). Change management interventions: Taking stock and moving forward. *Human Resource Management Review*, 34(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2023.101000>.
- Harsanto, B., Primiana, I., Sarasi, V., & Satyakti, Y. (2023). Sustainability Innovation in the Textile Industry: A Systematic Review. *Sustainability*, 15(2), 1549. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15021549>.
- Hiller Connell, K. Y., & Kozar, J. M. (2017). Introduction to special issue on sustainability and the triple bottom line within the global clothing and textiles industry. *Fashion and Textiles : International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 4(1), 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40691-017-0100-6>.
- Hossain, M. T., Shahid, M. A., Limon, M. G. M., Hossain, I., & Mahmud, N. (2024). Techniques, applications, and challenges in textiles for a sustainable future. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joitmc.2024.100230>.
- Huseyin Keles, Ozgur Yayla, Abdullah Tarinc, & Ali Keles. (2023). The Effect of Environmental Management Practices and Knowledge in Strengthening Responsible Behavior: The Moderator Role of Environmental Commitment. *Sustainability*, 15(2), 1398. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15021398>.
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). (2022, April 4). *The evidence is clear: the time for action is now. We can halve emissions by 2030*. IPCC. <https://www.ipcc.ch/2022/04/04/ipcc-ar6-wgiii-pressrelease/>.
- Iqbal, T., Shahzad, M. A., Alonso-Nuez, M. J., & Rosell-Martínez, J. (2022). Importance of environmental policy on firm performance for the textile industry: A contextual study of Pakistan. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1008890>.
- Islam, M. M., Perry, P., & Gill, S. (2020). Mapping environmentally sustainable practices in textiles, apparel and fashion industries: a systematic literature review. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal*, 25(2), 331–353. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFMM-07-2020-0130>.
- International Organization for Standardization. (2015). ISO 14001:2015 Environmental management systems. International Organization for Standardization. <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:14001:ed-3:v1:en>.
- International Organization for Standardization. (2006). ISO 14040:2006 Environmental management – Life cycle assessment. International Organization for Standardization. <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:14040:ed-2:v1:en>.
- International Organization for Standardization. (2015). ISO 9001:2015 Quality management systems. International Organization for Standardization. <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:9001:ed-5:v1:en>.
- Issa, A., Khadem, A., Alzubi, A., & Berberoğlu, A. (2024). The Path from Green Innovation to Supply Chain Resilience: Do Structural and Dynamic Supply Chain Complexity Matter? *Sustainability*, 16(9), 3762. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16093762>.
- Ivanović, T., Hischer, R., & Som, C. (2021). Bio-Based Polyester Fiber Substitutes: From GWP to a More Comprehensive Environmental Analysis. *Applied Sciences*, 11(7), 2993. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11072993>.
- Iyere, M., & Misopoulos, F. (2022). The degree of stakeholder influences and risks in sustainable supply chains: a systematic literature review. *International Journal of Contemporary Management*, 58(2), 9–26. <https://doi.org/10.2478/ijcm-2022-0004>.

- Javaid, M., Haleem, A., Pratap Singh, R., Khan, S., & Suman, R. (2022). Sustainability 4.0 and its applications in the field of manufacturing. *Internet of Things and Cyber-Physical Systems*, 2, 82–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iotcps.2022.06.001>.
- Jiang, L., Folmer, H., & Bu, M. (2016). Interaction between output efficiency and environmental efficiency: evidence from the textile industry in Jiangsu Province, China, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 113, 123-132. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.11.068>.
- Kafetzopoulos, D. P., Psomas, E. L., & Gotzamani, K. D. (2015). The impact of quality management systems on the performance of manufacturing firms. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 32(4), 381–399. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQRM-11-2013-0186>.
- Kähkönen, A.-K., Marttinen, K., Kontio, A., & Lintukangas, K. (2023). Practices and strategies for sustainability-related risk management in multi-tier supply chains. *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, 29(3). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pursup.2023.100848>.
- Kent, S. (2024, February 25). *Renewcell Files for Bankruptcy*. The Business of Fashion (BoF). <https://www.businessoffashion.com/news/sustainability/renewcell-bankruptcy-textile-recycling/>.
- Khairul Akter, M. M., Haq, U. N., Islam, M. M., & Uddin, M. A. (2022). Textile-apparel manufacturing and material waste management in the circular economy: A conceptual model to achieve sustainable development goal (SDG) 12 for Bangladesh. *Cleaner Environmental Systems*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cesys.2022.100070>.
- König, K., Mathieu, J., & Vielhaber, M. (2024). Resource conservation by means of lightweight design and design for circularity—A concept for decision making in the early phase of product development. *Resources, Conservation & Recycling*, 201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2023.107331>.
- Kounina, A., Daystar, J., Chalumeau, S., Devine, J., Geyer, R., Pires, S. T., Sonar, S. U., Venditti, R. A., & Boucher, J. (2024). The global apparel industry is a significant yet overlooked source of plastic leakage. *Nature Communications*, 15(1), 5022. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-49441-4>.
- Kumar, A., Kumar Shrivastav, S., Shrivastava, A. K., Panigrahi, R. R., Mardani, A., & Cavallaro, F. (2023). Sustainable Supply Chain Management, Performance Measurement, and Management: A Review. *Sustainability*, 15(5290), 5290. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15065290>.
- Kumar, L., Nadeem, F., Sloan, M., Restle-Steinert, J., Deitch, M. J., Naqvi, S. A., Kumar, A., & Sassanelli, C. (2022). Fostering Green Finance for Sustainable Development: A Focus on Textile and Leather Small Medium Enterprises in Pakistan. *Sustainability*, 14(19), 11908. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141911908>.
- Kumar, R., Verma, A., Shome, A., Sinha, R., Sinha, S., Kumar Jha, P., Kumar, R., Kumar, P., Shubham, Das, S., Sharma, P., & Vara Prasad, P. V. (2021). Impacts of Plastic Pollution on Ecosystem Services, Sustainable Development Goals, and Need to Focus on Circular Economy and Policy Interventions. *Sustainability*, 13(17), 9963. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13179963>.
- Kumar, V., Agrawal, T. K., Wang, L., & Chen, Y. (2017). Contribution of traceability towards attaining sustainability in the textile sector. *Textiles and Clothing Sustainability*, 3(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40689-017-0027-8>.
- Kumari, M., Berry, S., Agrawal, P.R. (2024). *Environmental Management System and Sustainable Textile Production*. In: Singh, P. (eds) Dye Pollution from Textile Industry. SDGs and Textiles. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-5341-3_12.

- Latip, M., Sharkawi, I., Mohamed, Z., & Kasron, N. (2022). The Impact of External Stakeholders' Pressures on the Intention to Adopt Environmental Management Practices and the Moderating Effects of Firm Size. *Journal of Small Business Strategy*, 32(3). <https://doi.org/10.53703/001c.35342>.
- Leahu-Aluas, S., & Burstein, E. P. (2010). Sustainable Manufacturing: An Essential Component of the Global 'Clean' Economy. *Manufacturing Engineering*, 145(1), 13-14.
- Leal Filho, W., Dinis, M. A. P., Liakh, O., Paço, A., Dennis, K., Shollo, F., & Sidsaph, H. (2024). Reducing the carbon footprint of the textile sector: an overview of impacts and solutions. *Textile Research Journal*, 94(15-16), 1798–1814. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00405175241236971>.
- Lectra. (2024). *Valia Fashion*. Lectra. <https://www.lectra.com/en/fashion/products/valia-fashion>.
- Lellis, B., Fávoro-Polonio, C. Z., Pamphile, J. A., & Polonio, J. C. (2019). Effects of textile dyes on health and the environment and bioremediation potential of living organisms. *Biotechnology Research and Innovation*, 3(2), 275–290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biori.2019.09.001>.
- Leventon, J., Buhr, M., Kessler, L., Rodriguez Aboytes, J. G., & Beyers, F. (2023). Processes of sustainability transformation across systems scales: leveraging systemic change in the textile sector. *Sustainability Science*, 19(2), 469–488. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-023-01436-8>.
- Li, B., & Wu, K. (2017). Environmental Management System Adoption and the Operational Performance of Firm in the Textile and Apparel Industry of China. *Sustainability*, 9(6), 992. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9060992>.
- Li, Y., & Wang, Y. (2019). Double decoupling effectiveness of water consumption and wastewater discharge in China's textile industry based on water footprint theory. *PeerJ*, 7, e6937. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.6937>.
- Li, Y., Lu, L., Tan, Y., Wang, L., & Shen, M. (2017). Decoupling Water Consumption and Environmental Impact on Textile Industry by Using Water Footprint Method: A Case Study in China. *Water*, 9(2), 124. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w9020124>.
- Li, Y., Lu, Q., Xing, Y., Liu, K., Ling, W., Yang, J., Yang, Q., Wu, T., Zhang, J., Pei, Z., Gao, Z., Li, X., Yang, F., Ma, H., Liu, K., & Zhao, D. (2023). Review of research on migration, distribution, biological effects, and analytical methods of microfibers in the environment. *Science of the Total Environment*, 855. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.158922>.
- Lifset, R., Kalimo, H., Jukka, A., Kautto, P., & Miettinen, M. (2023). Restoring the incentives for eco-design in extended producer responsibility: The challenges for eco-modulation. *Waste Management*, 168, 189–201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2023.05.033>.
- Lim, J., Choi, J., Won, A., Kim, M., Kim, S., & Yun, C. (2022). Cause of microfibers found in the domestic washing process of clothing, focusing on the manufacturing, wearing, and washing processes. *Fashion and Textiles : International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40691-022-00306-8>.
- Lindah, E. (2024). Circular production operations - A management system's framework for seamless transition from linear to circular. *Cleaner Environmental Systems*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cesys.2024.100191>.
- Liu, J., Liang, J., Ding, J., Zhang, G., Zeng, X., Yang, Q., Zhu, B., & Gao, W. (2021). Microfiber pollution: an ongoing major environmental issue related to the sustainable development of textile and clothing industry. *Environment, Development and Sustainability : A Multidisciplinary Approach to the Theory and Practice of Sustainable Development*, 23(8), 11240–11256. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-020-01173-3>.

- Loo, S.-L., Yu, E., & Hu, X. (2023). Tackling critical challenges in textile circularity: A review on strategies for recycling cellulose and polyester from blended fabrics. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, 11(5). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2023.110482>.
- Lorente-Leyva, L. L., Alemany, M. M. E., & Peluffo-Ordóñez, D. H. (2024). A conceptual framework for the operations planning of the textile supply chains: Insights for sustainable and smart planning in uncertain and dynamic contexts. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, 187. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cie.2023.109824>.
- Luoma, P., Penttinen, E., Tapio, P., & Toppinen, A. (2022). Future images of data in circular economy for textiles. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.121859>.
- Luo, Y., Song, K., Ding, X., & Wu, X. (2021). Environmental sustainability of textiles and apparel: A review of evaluation methods. *Environmental Impact Assessment Review*, 86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eiar.2020.106497>.
- Ly, B. (2021). Competitive advantage and internationalization of a circular economy model in apparel multinationals. *Cogent Business & Management*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2021.1944012>.
- Madhu, A., & Chakraborty, J. N. (2017). Developments in application of enzymes for textile processing. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 145, 114–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.01.013>.
- Madumali, S., Weerasinghe, B. A., Thibbotuwawa, A. & Perera, H. N. (2023). Transparency in textile & apparel supply chains: a systematic review. *Journal of South Asian Logistics and Transport*, 3(2), 71–101. <https://doi.org/10.4038/jsalt.v3i2.71>.
- Maia, L.C., Alves, A.C., Leão, C.P. (2019). *Implementing Lean Production to Promote Textile and Clothing Industry Sustainability*. In: Alves, A., Kahlen, F.J., Flumerfelt, S., Siriban-Manalang, A. (eds) *Lean Engineering for Global Development*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-13515-7_11.
- Malizia, A., & Monmany-Garzia, A. C. (2019). Terrestrial ecologists should stop ignoring plastic pollution in the Anthropocene time. *Science of the Total Environment*, 668, 1025–1029. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.03.044>.
- Matarneh, S., Piprani, A. Z., Ellahi, R. M., Nguyen, D. N., Mai Le, T., & Nazir, S. (2024). Industry 4.0 technologies and circular economy synergies: Enhancing corporate sustainability through sustainable supply chain integration and flexibility. *Environmental Technology & Innovation*, 35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eti.2024.103723>.
- McCay, J., & Mehta, S. (2024). Microfiber Fragment Pollution: Sources, Toxicity, Strategies, and Technologies for Remediation. *Sustainability*, 16(7), 3077. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16073077>.
- Mondejar, M. E., Avtar, R., Diaz, H. L. B., Dubey, R. K., Esteban, J., Gómez-Morales, A., Hallam, B., Mbungu, N. T., Okolo, C. C., Prasad, K. A., She, Q., & Garcia-Segura, S. (2021). Digitalization to achieve sustainable development goals: Steps towards a Smart Green Planet. *Science of the Total Environment*, 794. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.148539>.
- Muthu, S. S. (2020). *Assessing the environmental impact of textiles and the clothing supply chain* (2nd ed). Woodhead Publishing. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/book/9780128197837>.
- Napper, I. E., & Thompson, R. C. (2020). Plastic Debris in the Marine Environment: History and Future Challenges. *Global Challenges*, 4(6). <https://doi.org/10.1002/gch2.201900081>.

- Napper, I. E., Parker-Jurd, F. N. F., Wright, S. L., & Thompson, R. C. (2023). Examining the release of synthetic microfibres to the environment via two major pathways: Atmospheric deposition and treated wastewater effluent. *Science of the Total Environment*, 857. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.159317>.
- Nazir, S., Zhaolei, L., Mehmood, S., & Nazir, Z. (2024). Impact of Green Supply Chain Management Practices on the Environmental Performance of Manufacturing Firms Considering Institutional Pressure as a Moderator. *Sustainability*, 16(6), 2278. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16062278>.
- Nemlioglu, I., & Mallick, S. K. (2020). Do innovation-intensive firms mitigate their valuation uncertainty during bad times?. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 177, 913-940, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jebo.2020.06.004>.
- Orisadare, E. A., Achukwu, O. E., Ogunyemi, A. A., Adedeji, D. O., Diyaolu, I. J., Ugwu, E. I., Oluwatope, A. O., Bakare, K. O., & Awoyelu, I. O. (2024) Digitalisation and Green Strategies: A systematic review of the Textile, Apparel and Fashion Industries, 28 July 2024, PREPRINT (Version 1) available at *Research Square*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4804089/v1>.
- Osei, M. B., Papadopoulos, T., Acquaye, A., & Stamati, T. (2023). Improving sustainable supply chain performance through organisational culture: A competing values framework approach. *Journal of Purchasing and Supply Management*, 29(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pursup.2023.100821>.
- Ospital, P., Masson, D., Beler, C., & Legardeur, J. (2023). Toward product transparency: communicating traceability information to consumers. *International Journal of Fashion Design, Technology and Education*, 16(2), 186–197. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17543266.2022.2142677>.
- Palacios-Marín, A. V., Jabbar, A., & Tausif, M. (2022). Fragmented fiber pollution from common textile materials and structures during laundry. *Textile Research Journal*, 92(13-14), 2265–2275. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00405175221090971>.
- Palacios-Mateo, C., van der Meer, Y., & Seide, G. (2021). Analysis of the polyester clothing value chain to identify key intervention points for sustainability. *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 33(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-020-00447-x>.
- Pazilov, G. A., Ivashchenko, N. P., Bimendiyeva, L. A., & Aitymbetova, A. N. (2020). Textile industry : issues of managing the growth of innovative activity in enterprises. *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.17512/pjms.2020.21.1.22>.
- Patel, M., Sahu, A., & Rajak, R. (2021). *Solid Waste Management in Textile Industry*. In: Baskar, C., Ramakrishna, S., Baskar, S., Sharma, R., Chinnappan, A., Sehrawat, R. (eds) Handbook of Solid Waste Management. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-7525-9_57-1.
- Patnaik, S., & Tshifularo, Cyrus. (2021). *Redesigning of fashion supply chain*. Waste Management in the Fashion and Textile Industries (pp.265-274) <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-818758-6.00014-4>.
- Pedersen, E. R. G., Gwozdz, W., & Hvass, K. K. (2016). Exploring the Relationship Between Business Model Innovation, Corporate Sustainability, and Organisational Values within the Fashion Industry. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 149, 267–284. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-016-3044-7>.
- Peng, S-Y., Liu, J-Y., & Yong, G. (2022). Assessing Strategies for Reducing the Carbon Footprint of Textile Products in China under the shared Socio-Economic Pathways Framework. *Climate Change Economics*, 13, <https://doi.org.10.1142/S2010007822400048>.

- Petrillo, A., Rehman, M., & Baffo, I. (2024). Digital and Sustainable Transition in Textile Industry through Internet of Things Technologies: A Pakistani Case Study. *Applied Sciences*, 14(13), 5380. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app14135380>.
- Phys.Org. (2023, May 24). *New study finds bio-based plastic and plastic-blend textiles do not biodegrade in the ocean*. University of California. Phys.Org. <https://phys.org/news/2023-05-bio-based-plastic-plastic-blend-textiles-biodegrade.html>.
- Pinkse, J., Demirel, P., & Marino, A. (2024). Unlocking innovation for net zero: constraints, enablers, and firm-level transition strategies. *Industry and Innovation*, 31(1), 16–41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13662716.2023.2269112>.
- Prasad, D. S., Pradhan, R. P., Gaurav, K., & Sabat, A. K. (2020). Critical Success Factors of Sustainable Supply Chain Management and Organizational Performance: An Exploratory Study. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 48, 327–344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2020.08.027>.
- Priya, K. K., Thilagam, H., Muthukumar, T., Gopalakrishnan, S., & Govarathanan, M. (2023). Impact of microfiber pollution on aquatic biota: A critical analysis of effects and preventive measures. *Science of the Total Environment*, 887. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.163984>.
- Qian, W., Ji, X., Xu, P., & Wang, L. (2021). Carbon footprint and water footprint assessment of virgin and recycled polyester textiles. *Textile Research Journal*, 91(21-22), 2468–2475. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00405175211006213>.
- Rahaman, M. T., Pranta, A. D., Repon, M. R., Ahmed, M. S., & Islam, T. (2024). Green production and consumption of textiles and apparel: Importance, fabrication, challenges and future prospects. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joitmc.2024.100280>.
- Rahman, M., Hack-Polay, D., Billah, M. M., & Un Nabi, M. N. (2020). Bio-based textile processing through the application of enzymes for environmental sustainability. *International Journal of Technology Management & Sustainable Development*, 19(1), 87–106. https://doi.org/10.1386/tmsd_00017_1.
- Renewcell. (2024). CIRCULOSE®. <https://www.renewcell.com/en/circulose/>.
- Resta, B., & Dotti, S. (2015). Environmental impact assessment methods for textiles and clothing. In *Handbook of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of textiles and clothing* (pp. 149-191). Woodhead publishing.
- Resta, B., Gaiardelli, P., Pinto, R., & Dotti, S. (2016). Enhancing environmental management in the textile sector: An Organisational-Life Cycle Assessment approach. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 135, 620–632. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.06.135>.
- Rhodes, C. J. (2019). Solving the plastic problem: From cradle to grave, to reincarnation. *Science Progress*, 102(3), 218–248. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0036850419867204>.
- Ribul, M., Lanot, A., Tommencioni Pisapia, C., Purnell, P., McQueen-Mason, S. J., & Baurley, S. (2021). Mechanical, chemical, biological: Moving towards closed-loop bio-based recycling in a circular economy of sustainable textiles. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 326. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.129325>.
- Roberts, H., Milios, L., Mont, O., & Dalhammar, C. (2023). Product destruction: Exploring unsustainable production-consumption systems and appropriate policy responses. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 35, 300–312. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.11.009>.

- Rosenboom, J.-G., Langer, R., & Traverso, G. (2022). Bioplastics for a circular economy. *Nature Reviews Materials*, 7(2), 117–137. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41578-021-00407-8>.
- Roy, S., Das, M., Ali, S. M., Raihan, A. S., Paul, S. K., & Kabir, G. (2020). Evaluating strategies for environmental sustainability in a supply chain of an emerging economy. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121389>.
- Sahimaa, O., Miller, E. M., Halme, M., Niinimäki, K., Tanner, H., Mäkelä, M., Rissanen, M., Härrä, A., & Hummel, M. (2023). From Simplistic to Systemic Sustainability in the Textile and Fashion Industry. *Circular Economy and Sustainability*, 4(2), 1115–1131. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43615-023-00322-w>.
- Salmi, A., & Kaipia, R. (2022). Implementing circular business models in the textile and clothing industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 378. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.134492>.
- Sánchez-García, E., Martínez-Falcó, J., Marco-Lajara, B., & Manresa-Marhuenda, E. (2024). Revolutionizing the circular economy through new technologies: A new era of sustainable progress. *Environmental Technology & Innovation*, 33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eti.2023.103509>.
- Sandberg, E., & Pal, R. (2024). Exploring supply chain capabilities in textile-to-textile recycling - A European interview study. *Cleaner Logistics and Supply Chain*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clscn.2024.100152>.
- Science Based Targets Initiative (SBTi). (2017). *Apparel and footwear*. Science Based Targets Initiative. <https://sciencebasedtargets.org/sectors/apparel-and-footwear>.
- Shamsuzzaman, M., Islam, M. M., Hasan, H. M. R. U., Khan, A. M., & Sayem, A. S. M. (2023). Mapping environmental sustainability of knitted textile production facilities. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 405. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136900>.
- Sharma, B., Mittal, M. L., Soni, G., & Ramtiyal, B. (2023). An Implementation Framework for Resiliency Assessment in a Supply Chain. *Global Journal of Flexible Systems Management*, 24(4), 591–614. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40171-023-00348-x>.
- Shekarian, E., Ijadi, B., Zare, A., & Majava, J. (2022). Sustainable Supply Chain Management: A Comprehensive Systematic Review of Industrial Practices. *Sustainability*, 14(13), 7892. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14137892>.
- Shen, L., Worrell, E., & Patel, M. K. (2012). Comparing life cycle energy and GHG emissions of bio-based PET, recycled PET, PLA, and man-made cellulose. *Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining*, 6(6), 625–639. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bbb.1368>.
- Siegfried, M., Koelmans, A. A., Besseling, E., & Kroeze, C. (2017). Export of microplastics from land to sea. A modelling approach. *Water Research*, 127, 249–257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2017.10.011>.
- Silva, C., Cavaco-Paulo, A. M., & Fu, J. J. (2015). *Enzymatic biofinishes for synthetic textiles* (pp. 153-191). Woodhead Publishing: Cambridge.
- Singh, K., & Kumar, K. (2024). Micro- and Nanoplastic Pollution in the Anthropocene: Understanding and Addressing a Global Crisis. *Anthropocene Science*, 3, 143–149. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44177-024-00076-6>.
- Singh, N., Ogunseitan, O. A., Wong, M. H., & Tang, Y. (2022). Sustainable materials alternative to petrochemical plastics pollution: A review analysis. *Sustainable Horizons*, 2. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.horiz.2022.100016>.

- Singh, Z., & Bhalla, S. (2017). Toxicity of synthetic fibres & health. *Advance Research in Textile Engineering*, 2(1), 1-5.
- Srisawat, S., & Srisawat, N. (2020). The effect of green supply chain management practices on the sustainable performance of the textile industry. *International Journal of Supply Chain Management*, 9(2), 300-308. ISSN: 2050-7399 (Online), 2051-3771 (Print).
- Stahel, W.R. (2021). *The Circular Industrial Economy of the Anthropocene and Its Benefits to Society*. Handbook of Advanced Performability Engineering. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-55732-4_11.
- Stål, H. I., & Corvellec, H. (2018). A decoupling perspective on circular business model implementation: Illustrations from Swedish apparel. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 171, 630–643. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.09.249>.
- Stanton, T., Stanes, E., Gwinnett, C., Lei, X., Cauilan-Cureg, M., Ramos, M., Sallach, J. B., Harrison, E., Osborne, A., Sanders, C. H., Baynes, E., Law, A., Johnson, M., Ryves, D. B., Sheridan, K. J., Blackburn, R. S., & McKay, D. (2023). Shedding off-the-grid: The role of garment manufacturing and textile care in global microfibre pollution. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 428. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.139391>.
- Stulga, P., Whitfield, R. I., Love, J., & Evans, D. (2022). Towards Sustainable Manufacturing with Industry 4.0: A Framework for the Textile Industry. *Proceedings of the Design Society*, 2, 283–292. <https://doi.org/10.1017/pds.2022.30>.
- Sun, J., Sarfraz, M., Khawaja, K. F., & Abdullah, M. I. (2022). Sustainable Supply Chain Strategy and Sustainable Competitive Advantage: A Mediated and Moderated Model. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.895482>.
- Sun, X., Wang, X., Sun, F., Tian, M., Qu, L., Perry, P., Owens, H., & Liu, X. (2021). Textile Waste Fiber Regeneration via a Green Chemistry Approach: A Molecular Strategy for Sustainable Fashion. *Advanced Materials*, 33(48). <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202105174>.
- Surana, D., Vinay, Patel, P., Ghosh, P., Sharma, S., Kumar, V., & Kumar, S. (2024). Microplastic Fibers in Different Environmental Matrices from Synthetic Textiles: Ecotoxicological Risk, Mitigation Strategies, and Policy Perspective. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, 12(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2024.112333>.
- Tang, K. H. D. (2023). State of the Art in Textile Waste Management: A Review. *Textiles*, 3(4), 454–467. <https://doi.org/10.3390/textiles3040027>.
- Taylor, B. (2024, June 5). *Textile recycling plant acquired out of bankruptcy*. Waste Today Magazine. <https://www.wastetodaymagazine.com/news/renewcell-altor-purchase-sweden-cotton-textile-recycling/>.
- Textile Exchange. (2024). *Using Carbon Capture to Replace Fossil-Based Polyester Feedstocks with LanzaTech and On*. Textile Exchange. <https://textileexchange.org/carbon-capture-polyester-lanzatech-on/>.
- Textile Exchange. (2024, April 14). *The Future of Synthetics*. Textile Exchange. <https://textileexchange.org/knowledge-center/reports/the-future-of-synthetics/>.
- Textile Exchange. (2024, September). *Materials Market Report*. Textile Exchange. <https://textileexchange.org/knowledge-center/reports/materials-market-report-2024/>.
- The Microfibre Consortium. (2024). The Microfibre Consortium. <https://www.microfibreconsortium.com/>.

- Thorisdottir, T. S., & Johannsdottir, L. (2020). Corporate Social Responsibility Influencing Sustainability within the Fashion Industry. A Systematic Review. *Sustainability*, 12(9167), 9167. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12219167>.
- Tochetto, G. A., Aragão, A. M. I., de Oliveira, D., & Immich, A. P. S. (2022). Can enzymatic processes transform textile processes? A critical analysis of the industrial application. *Process Biochemistry*, 123, 27-35, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procbio.2022.10.030>.
- Tremblay, L. A., Ataria, J. M., Challenger, I., Horswell, J., Baker, V., Langer, E. R. L., Leckie, A., Champeau, O., Siggins, A., & Northcott, G. L. (2023). Up-the-Pipe Solutions: A Best Practice Framework to Engage Communities in Reducing Chemical Contamination in Waste. *Pollutants*, 3(4), 494–506. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pollutants3040034>.
- Ullah, A., Pinglu, C., Ullah, S., Zaman, M., & Hashmi, S. H. (2020). The nexus between capital structure, firm-specific factors, macroeconomic factors and financial performance in the textile sector of Pakistan. *Heliyon*, 6(8). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04741>.
- United Nations Environment Programme. (2022, November 24). *The environmental costs of fast fashion*. UN Environment Programme. <https://www.unep.org/news-and-stories/story/environmental-costs-fast-fashion>.
- United Nations Environment Programme. (2023, March 2). *Sustainability and Circularity in the Textile Value Chain - A Global Roadmap*. UN Environment Programme. <https://www.unep.org/resources/publication/sustainability-and-circularity-textile-value-chain-global-roadmap>.
- United Nations Environment Programme. (2024). *Trade in Environmentally Sound Technologies*. UN Environment Programme. <https://www.unep.org/regions/asia-and-pacific/regional-initiatives/supporting-resource-efficiency/environmentally-sound>.
- United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. (2018). *Fashion Industry Charter for Climate Action*. UNFCCC. <https://unfccc.int/climate-action/sectoral-engagement-for-climate-action/fashion-charter>.
- Villena, V. H., & Gioia, D. A. (2018). On the riskiness of lower-tier suppliers: Managing sustainability in supply networks. *Journal of Operations Management*, 64(1), 65–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jom.2018.09.004>.
- Wang, Y., Rehmani, M., Ashraf, M. R., Farheen, N., & Irshad, H. (2022). Comparing the EMS adopter and EMS non-adopter organizations in achieving sustainable business goals. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1009457>.
- Wani, K. A., & Nirmalā Kumārī. (2020). *Impact of textile dyes on public health and the environment*. IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-0311-9>.
- Warasthe, R., Brandenburg, M., & Seuring, S. (2022). Sustainability, risk and performance in textile and apparel supply chains. *Cleaner Logistics and Supply Chain*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clscn.2022.100069>.
- Wiedemann, S. G., Clarke, S. J., Nguyen, Q. V., Cheah, Z. X., & Simmons, A. T. (2023). Strategies to reduce environmental impacts from textiles: Extending clothing wear life compared to fibre displacement assessed using consequential LCA. *Resources, Conservation & Recycling*, 198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2023.107119>.
- Wong, D. T. W., & Ngai, E. W. T. (2022). Supply chain innovation: Conceptualization, instrument development, and influence on supply chain performance. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 39(2), 132–159. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpim.12612>.

- Wren, B. (2022). Sustainable supply chain management in the fast fashion Industry: A comparative study of current efforts and best practices to address the climate crisis. *Cleaner Logistics and Supply Chain*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clscn.2022.100032>.
- Xu, C., Cheng, H., & Liao, Z. (2018) Towards Sustainable Growth in the Textile Industry: A Case Study of Environmental Policy in China. *Polish Journal of Environmental Studies*, 27(5), 2325-2336. <https://doi.org/10.15244/pjoes/79720>.
- Yang, R., Xu, G., Tao, W., Wang, Q., & Tang, Y. (2024). Recycled polymer: Green roads for polyester plastics. *Green Carbon*, 2(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.greenca.2024.01.004>.
- Yang, Y., Chen, J., Lee, P. K. C., & Cheng, T. C. E. (2023). How to enhance the effects of the green supply chain management strategy in the organization: A diffusion process perspective. *Transportation Research Part E*, 175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2023.103148>.
- Yu, H., Ahn, M., & Han, E. (2023). Key driver of textile and apparel industry management: fashion brand ESG and brand reputation. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2023.1140004>.
- Zhang, J., Qian, X., & Feng, J. (2020). Review of carbon footprint assessment in textile industry. *Ecofeminism and Climate Change*, 1(1), 51–56. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EFCC-03-2020-0006>.
- Zhang, Y., & Berhe, H. M. (2022). The Impact of Green Investment and Green Marketing on Business Performance: The Mediation Role of Corporate Social Responsibility in Ethiopia's Chinese Textile Companies. *Sustainability*, 14(7), 3883. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14073883>.
- Zhou, J., & Jin, S. (2023). Corporate Environmental Protection Behavior and Sustainable Development: The Moderating Role of Green Investors and Green Executive Cognition. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(4179), 4179. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20054179>.
- Zimon, D. (2020). ISO 14001 AND THE CREATION OF SSCM IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY. *International Journal for Quality Research*, 14(3), 739–748. <https://doi.org/10.24874/IJQR14.03-06>.
- Zimon, D., Madzík, P., Dellana, S., Sroufe, R., Ikram, M., & Lysenko-Ryba, K. (2022). Environmental effects of ISO 9001 and ISO 14001 management system implementation in SSCM. *The TQM Journal*, 34(3), 418–447. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-01-2021-0025>.
- Zimon, D., Madzík, P., & Sroufe, R. (2020). The Influence of ISO 9001 & ISO 14001 on Sustainable Supply Chain Management in the Textile Industry. *Sustainability*, 12(4282), 4282. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12104282>.